

Solvent hydrogen bonding and structural effects on nucleophilic substitution reactions. Part-1 : Reaction of benzenesulphonyl chloride with anilines in benzene/2-methylpropan-2-ol-mixtures

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Abstract : Substitution reactions of eleven *para*- and *meta*-substituted anilines with benzenesulphonyl chloride in different mole fractions of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol have been investigated conductometrically. The second order rate constants don't correlate either with pK_a values of the anilines or with the Hammett's and its modified equations. The *para*-substituted anilines shows a satisfactory correlation with Charton's LDR equation and the results indicate the formation of an electron deficient transition state. The rate data correlate satisfactorily with macroscopic solvent parameters such as relative permittivity, ϵ_r , and polarity, E_T^N . Multiple correlation analysis of the rate data via Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters reveals that the solvent hydrogen bond donor property plays a dominant role in governing the reactivity.

Keywords : Substitution, benzenesulphonyl chloride, solvent effect.

The study of solute-solvent interactions in binary mixtures is more complex than in pure solvents. In a pure solvent the composition of the microsphere of solvation of a solute, the so called cybotatic region, is the same as in the bulk solvent, but in binary mixtures the composition in this microsphere can be different. The solute can interact to a different degree with the components of the mixture, and this difference in the interactions is reflected in the composition of the microsphere of solvation. The effect of varying the composition of the mixture from the bulk solvent to the solvation sphere is called preferential solvation¹.

Examination of the literature reveals that the effects of structure on S_N2 reactions have largely been reported²⁻⁶. However, literature lacks a systematic study on the effect of solvent on such reactions. Hence, a systematic study of various LFERs and the isokinetic relationship has been made to establish the role of solvent and substituents on reactivity and to decide the nature of the mechanism followed in the reaction of several *meta*- and *para*-substituted anilines with benzenesulphonyl chloride in benzene/2-methylpropan-2-ol mixtures of varying compositions. This mixture is so chosen that by varying the mole fraction of the constituent solvents, the hydrogen bonding properties of the medium can be varied in a smooth and continuous manner since 2-methylpropan-2-

ol is classified as a typical hydrogen bond donor (HBD) and benzene as a typical non-hydrogen bond donor (non-HBD) solvent⁷.

Results and discussion

The nucleophilic substitution reaction of aniline and *para*-(Me, COMe, NHCOMe, NO₂, Br, Cl, F) and *meta*-(Me, NO₂, COMe) substituted anilines were studied conductometrically at three different temperatures in the presence of varying excess of the aniline over the substrate to ensure first-order kinetics. The second-order rate constants, k_2 , computed and are summarized in Table 1. The reactions were carried out in varying mole fractions of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol. The selection of the mole fractions was based on the fact that the solvatochromic parameters employed in the present study for correlation analysis are available in the literature¹. The overall reaction is represented as follows.

Survey of literature shows that the generally accepted mechanism of S_N2 reactions of anilines with benzenesulphonyl chlorides² and other aromatic sulphonyl chlorides⁸ is well established and involves a transition state (1) as given below.

The results in Table 1 reveal that increase in mole fraction of 2-methylpropan-2-ol in the mixture increases the rate of the reaction. Fig. 1 shows the solution FT-IR spectrum of the reaction mixture at different time intervals. The doublet around 3390–3475 cm^{-1} corresponds to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the two N–H bonds of the aromatic primary amine. It is evident from the figure that with increase in time the intensity of the peak decreases which confirms the participation of the amine group in the reaction.

Thermodynamic parameters and the isokinetic relationship :

The activation parameters were calculated from k_2 at 308, 318 and 328 K using the van't Hoff plot by the method of least squares and are collected in Table 2. The operation of isokinetic relationship is tested by plotting the logarithms of rate constants at two temperatures ($T_2 > T_1$) against each other according to eq. (1) as suggested by Exner⁹.

$$\log k \text{ (at } T_2) = a + b \log k \text{ (at } T_1) \quad (1)$$

In the present study linear plots imply the validity of isokinetic relationship. A representative plot is shown in

Fig. 2 (in 0.0080 mole fraction of benzene, $r = 0.803$, $sd = 0.099$, isokinetic temperature = 291 ± 17 K). The operation of isokinetic relationship reveals that all the substituted anilines examined follow a common mechanism.

The activation energies and the entropies and enthalpies of activation were also calculated for the reaction in eight different mole fractions of benzene (Table 3). Negative entropy of activation indicates a greater degree of ordering in the transition state than in the initial state, due to an increase in solvation during the activation process. The existence of a linear relationship (Fig. 3, $r = 0.975$, $sd = 0.050$, isokinetic temperature = 278 ± 13 K) between $\log k_2$ at 328 K and $\log k_2$ at 318 K indicates that a single mechanism is operating in all the solvent systems studied.

Solvent-reactivity correlation : The title reaction has been studied in eight different mole fractions of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol. The second order rate constants presented in Table 1 increase with increase in mole fraction of 2-methylpropan-2-ol in the mixture. The rate data (Table 1) correlates satisfactorily with relative permittivity of the medium, ϵ_r , through Laidler-Eyring¹⁰ equation (Explained variance, $100r^2 > 90$) and a representative plot is shown in Fig. 4 and also with Reichard's⁷ polarity parameters E_T^N ($100r^2 > 95$) and a representative plot is shown in Fig. 5. These bulk solvent properties will poorly describe the microenvironment around the reacting species, which governs the stability of the transition state and hence the rate of the reaction.

Therefore, in order to obtain a deeper insight into the various solvent-solvent-solute interactions, which

Table 1. Second order rate constants ($10^4 k_2$, s^{-1}) for the substitution of anilines in varying mole fraction of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol

R^a	Mole fraction of benzene							
	0	0.008	0.021	0.041	0.060	0.096	0.130	0.150
H	16.13	16.12	13.62	12.36	12.19	12.18	10.66	8.780
<i>p</i> -Me	19.02	18.03	17.89	14.81	14.41	14.24	13.99	11.37
<i>p</i> -COMe	14.28	13.36	13.33	10.39	9.760	9.540	7.060	6.440
<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	18.45	18.25	17.95	15.89	15.56	12.45	11.44	9.460
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	15.60	14.84	15.26	12.43	11.20	9.650	9.240	8.560
<i>p</i> -Cl	14.46	14.22	13.06	12.87	12.78	12.32	12.07	10.91
<i>p</i> -Br	17.89	15.12	14.68	14.36	13.35	12.28	12.02	10.91
<i>p</i> -F	14.13	13.39	15.26	12.43	11.20	9.650	9.240	8.560
<i>m</i> -Me	15.17	11.31	10.79	10.43	10.12	9.850	9.110	7.340
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	16.75	12.87	11.72	11.00	9.920	9.320	9.110	7.470
<i>m</i> -COMe	19.19	18.85	18.96	16.66	15.13	12.90	12.12	12.07

^aSubstituent in aniline moiety.

Table 2. Effect of temperature on the rate of substitution reaction of anilines by benzenesulphonyl chloride in 0.008 mole fraction of benzene and activation parameters for the reaction

Substituents in aniline	Rate constants $10^4 k_2, \text{s}^{-1}$			E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
	308 K	318 K	328 K				
H	16.12	25.16	35.43	33	30	-202	92.4
<i>p</i> -Me	18.03	20.16	31.87	24	21	-230	92.2
<i>p</i> -COMe	13.36	13.90	14.33	3	30	-299	92.5
<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	18.25	19.50	40.77	33	31	-200	92.4
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	14.84	28.63	34.36	35	32	-195	92.5
<i>p</i> -Cl	14.22	15.56	16.59	3	4	-287	92.4
<i>p</i> -Br	15.12	16.31	26.39	23	21	-234	92.6
<i>p</i> -F	13.39	17.88	19.02	15	12	-261	92.6
<i>m</i> -Me	11.31	17.62	24.63	32	30	-206	93.3
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	12.87	15.44	17.41	13	10	-268	92.7
<i>m</i> -COMe	18.85	21.26	34.43	25	22	-226	92.1

E_a in $\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$; ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$; ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1} .

influence reactivity, we have tried to adopt the solvatochromic comparison method developed by Kamlet and Taft¹¹. The kinetic data were correlated with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* in the form of the following Linear Solvation Energy Relationship (LSER).

$$\log k = A_0 + s \pi^* + a \alpha + b \beta \quad (2)$$

where, π^* = solvent dipolarity/polarizability, α = solvent hydrogen bond donor acidity (HBD), β = solvent hydrogen bond acceptor basicity (HBA).

The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k$ to the indicated solvent parameter. The rates

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectra of the reaction mixture in benzene with increase in time.

Fig. 2. The isokinetic plot for the oxidation of anilines in 0.0080 mole fraction of benzene.

of the reaction for all the compounds studied show a good correlation with solvent via the above LSER (eq. (2)) with an explained variance of *ca.* 95%. Such a good correlation indicates the existence of both specific and non-specific solute-solvent interactions in the present study.

From the values of the regression coefficients the contribution of each parameter, on a percentage basis, to reactivity were calculated and are listed in Table 4. The observation of this multiple regression analysis leads us to the following conclusions. (i) The rate of the reaction is strongly influenced by specific solute-solvent interactions as indicated by the percentage contributions of α and β parameters. (ii) The positive sign of the coefficients of α

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters and rate constants ($10^4 k_2, s^{-1}$) for the substitution of aniline by benzenesulphonyl chloride in various mole fraction of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol

Mole fraction of benzene	Rate constants $10^4 k_2, s^{-1}$,			E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
	308 K	318 K	328 K				
0	16.13	29.20	37.89	36	33	-193	92.3
0.008	16.12	25.16	35.43	33	30	-202	92.4
0.021	13.62	13.63	20.20	16	14	-256	92.8
0.041	12.36	13.06	15.54	9	7	-279	92.8
0.060	12.19	12.76	13.95	6	3	-291	92.7
0.096	12.18	12.63	13.73	5	2	-293	92.8
0.130	10.66	12.06	12.45	6	4	-289	93.1
0.151	8.78	9.78	10.61	8	5	-286	93.6

E_a in $\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$; ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$; ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1} .

and β terms suggest that the specific interaction between the transition state and the solvent is more than that between the reactants and the solvent. (iii) The solvent HBD acidity, as indicated by the α term, plays a dominant role in governing the reactivity. It alone explains over 52% of the observed solvent effect on the reactivity. This may be due to the fact that, from **1** it is evident that the removal of chloride ion will be facilitated with increase in hydrogen bond donor property of the solvent. Parallel to this expectation the rate of the reaction increase with increase in mole fraction of 2-methylpropan-2-ol in the mixture. (iv) The solvent polarizability/dipolarity, as indicated by P_{π^*} , also plays an appreciable role in governing the reactivity. The negative sign of the coefficient of this term suggests that with increase in polarizability/dipolarity of the medium the rate of the reaction will decrease. Since benzene is a more polarizable solvent ($\delta = 1$) than 2-methylpropan-2-ol ($\delta = 0$)¹, an increase in its mole fraction in the mixture increases the polarizability of the medium and consequently decreases the rate of the reaction.

The observed effects of the medium on the reaction in the present investigation may be summarized as follows. The increase in rate of reaction with increase in the mole fraction of 2-methylpropan-2-ol in the mixture could be due to

- Increase in relative permittivity of the medium thereby increasing the rate of reaction due to the extra stabilization of the intermediate first formed from the reaction of the nucleophile with the substrate. This was supported by the correlation of rate data with Laidler-Eyring and Reichardt solvent polarity indices.
- Increase in the mole fraction of 2-methylpropan-2-

ol in the mixture and consequent interaction of it with any zwitter ionic intermediate formed as in (**1**) would assist the expulsion of the leaving group through hydrogen bonding thus leading to an increase in the rate of reaction. This is well supported by the results of the Kamlet-Taft correlation.

Structure-reactivity correlation : The effect of substituents on the rate was studied with 11 *para*- and *meta*-substituted anilines (Table 1). The results reveal that in a given mole fraction the rate constants vary with the nature of the substrate. The rate data do not correlate with $\text{p}K_a$ values of anilines. The rate data also failed to conform to either the usual Hammett equation or its modified ones; plots of $\log k_2$ versus substituent constants are non-linear

Fig. 3. The isokinetic plot for the substitution reaction of aniline in varying mole fractions.

Table 4. Statistical results and weighted percentage contributions for the correlation of $\log k_2$ with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^*

Substituent	100R ²	sd	a	b	s	P _{α}	P _{β}	P _{π^*}
H	97	0.02	7.96	0.60	-1.49	79	6	15
<i>p</i> -Me	92	0.03	4.43	0.44	-3.45	53	5	42
<i>p</i> -COMe	93	0.04	2.43	1.68	-3.76	31	21	48
<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	96	0.03	0.83	1.35	-4.85	12	19	69
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	97	0.02	-0.73	1.56	-4.03	12	25	64
<i>p</i> -Cl	99	0.01	3.67	0.28	-0.48	83	6	11
<i>p</i> -Br	95	0.02	2.68	0.88	-0.96	59	19	21
<i>p</i> -F	94	0.02	4.69	-0.07	-7.60	38	1	61
<i>m</i> -Me	87	0.04	7.54	0.73	-0.35	87	9	4
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	93	0.04	7.45	1.10	-0.84	79	12	9
<i>m</i> -COMe	99	0.01	-2.02	1.54	-2.81	32	24	44

Fig. 4. The plot of $\log k_2$ vs $1/\epsilon_s$.

Fig. 5. Plot of $\log k_2$ versus E_T^N .

(not shown). The dual substituent parameter (DSP) equations^{12,13} also failed to correlate the rate data with the substituent.

The rate constants were, therefore, analyzed in terms of LDR equation (eq. (3)) introduced by Charton¹⁴ for the quantitative description of structural effects on chemical reactivities.

$$\log k = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_d + R\sigma_e + h \quad (3)$$

where, σ_1 is a localized (field and/or inductive) effect parameter, σ_d is the intrinsic delocalized (resonance) electrical effect parameter when active site electronic demand is minimal and σ_e represents the sensitivity of the substituent to change in electronic demand by the active site. L, D and R are the coefficients of the σ_1 , σ_d and σ_e

parameters respectively. The triparametric model results from the fact that substituent types differ in their mode of electron delocalization. This difference is reflected in a different sensitivity to the electronic demand of the phenomenon being studied. The latter two substituent parameters are related as :

$$\sigma_D = \eta\sigma_e + \sigma_d \quad (4)$$

where, η represents the electronic demand of the reaction site which is given by $\eta = R/D$, and σ_D represents the delocalized electrical parameter of the diparametric LD equation which varies with the magnitude and sign of η .

The rates of the reaction of the *para*-substituted anilines showed a good correlation with LDR equation and the statistical parameters are collected in Table 5. Due to lack

Table 5. Results of the correlation analysis of the rate data of anilines-benzenesulphonyl chloride reaction with LDR parameters

Mole fraction of benzene	L	D	R	η	R^2	sd	Ψ	P_D
0	-0.201(0.10) ^a	-0.191(0.10)	-0.609(0.46)	3.19	0.961	0.05	0.26	49
0.0080	-0.257(0.04)	-0.216(0.04)	-0.642(0.18)	2.97	0.946	0.02	0.30	46
0.0210	-0.226(0.06)	-0.247(0.07)	-1.026(0.30)	4.15	0.985	0.03	0.16	52
0.0411	-0.168(0.07)	-0.309(0.07)	-0.616(0.31)	1.99	0.966	0.03	0.24	65
0.0605	-0.212(0.07)	-0.327(0.08)	-0.701(0.35)	2.14	0.959	0.03	0.26	61
0.0969	-0.156(0.05)	-0.156(0.06)	-0.004(0.35)	0.02	0.994	0.03	0.10	50
0.1300	-0.264(0.14)	-0.356(0.15)	-0.174(0.66)	0.49	0.941	0.07	0.32	57
0.1500	-0.198(0.21)	-0.273(0.22)	-0.107(1.0)	0.39	0.981	0.10	0.39	58

^aValues in parentheses are the standard errors.

of the minimum required number of data points, to correlate with LDR equation, the *meta*-substituents are not included. The comparison of the L and D values for the substituted anilines showed that the reaction of *para*-substituted anilines is more susceptible to the delocalised effect than the localized effect. All the regression coefficients, L, D and R are negative indicating an electron-deficient reaction center in the transition state of the reaction. The positive value of η adds a negative increment to σ_d (eq. (4)), increasing the donor effect of the substituent where σ_d is negative and decreasing the acceptor effect where σ_d is positive. The substituent is therefore better able to stabilize a cationic or electronically deficient reaction site. This also supports the presence of an electron-deficient center in the transition state of the rate-determining step. This observation supports the nature of the transition state as given (1). The percent contribution of the delocalized effect, P_D is given by the following equation.

$$P_D = (|D| \times 100) / (|L| + |D|) \quad (5)$$

The values of P_D and P_L are also recorded in Table 5. The value of P_D for the reaction of *para*-substituted aniline is dominant, *ca.* 55%, as spelt above.

Conclusion :

The solution FT-IR studies show that, the substitution reaction involves a transition state in which the amine group is participating. The results of the correlation of rate data with LDR equation suggest an electron-deficient reaction center in the transition state of the reaction. The correlation of the reaction rates with solvent via Kamlet-Taft equation indicates the existence of both specific and

non-specific solute-solvent interactions in the present study. Further hydrogen bonding donor (HBD) ability of the solvent plays a major role in governing the reactivity and the rate of the reaction was found to increase with increase in HBD property of the medium. The formation of a transition state as depicted in (1) is well supported by the solvent and structural effects.

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals (Aldrich or Merck, India) used were of analytical grade. The solvents 2-methylpropan-2-ol and benzene were of chromatographic grade and used as received. The solid anilines were used as such and the liquid anilines were used after vacuum distillation.

Kinetic studies : The reactions of benzenesulphonyl chloride with substituted anilines in varying mole fractions of benzene in 2-methylpropan-2-ol were followed conductometrically at 35, 45 and 55 \pm 0.1 $^{\circ}$ C. The concentration of benzenesulphonyl chloride was 5×10^{-4} M and that of aniline was between 0.01 to 0.02 M. Pseudo-first order conditions were used in all cases. Regression coefficients of all the reaction rate constants were around 0.99. The reaction is so slow that it is inconvenient to wait for its completion. Therefore, the Guggenheim method¹⁵ was used to evaluate the rate constants by carrying out the kinetic runs for up to 3 h. The second-order rate constants, k_2 , were obtained from the observed rate constants as reported earlier¹⁶. All rate determinations were carried out at least in duplicate and the rate constants are accurate to within \pm 2%. The solution IR experiment was done with a horizontal attenuated total reflectance ZnSe flat prism plate, in a JASCO FT-IR 460 Plus spectrometer.

Data analysis : Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal Origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient and standard deviation, sd^{17} . The percentage contribution (P_{χ}) of a parameter to the total effect on reactivity was computed using the regression coefficient of each parameter as reported earlier¹⁸.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out, under kinetic conditions, by employing GC-MS. The results of the GC-MS analysis reveal that the reaction products were benzene sulphonyl (aniline) (m/z 233) and anilinium ion (m/z 94).

References

1. E. Bosch, F. Rived and M. Roses, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1996, 2177.
2. I. Lee and I. S. Koo, *Tetrahedron*, 1983, **39**, 1803.
3. I. Lee, W. H. Lee, S. C. Sohn and C. S. Kim, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, **41**, 2635.
4. S. W. Hong, H. J. Koh, H. W. Lee and I. Lee, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **20**, 1172.
5. O. Rogne, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 1856.
6. H. W. Lee, A. K. Guha and I. Lee, *Tetrahedron*, 2002, **34**, 632.
7. C. Reichardt, "Solvents and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry", VCH, Weinheim, 1988.
8. A. Arcoria, V. Librando, E. Maccarone, G. Musumarra and G. A. Tomaselli, *Tetrahedron*, 1977, **33**, 105.
9. L. Liu and Q. Guo, *Chem. Rev.*, 2001, **101**, 673.
10. E. S. Amis and J. I. Hinton, "Solvent Effect of Chemical Phenomena", Academic Press, New York, 1973.
11. M. J. Kamlet, J. M. Abboud, M. H. Abraham and R. W. Taft, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 2877.
12. S. K. Dayal, S. Ehrenson and R. W. Taft, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 9113.
13. C. G. Swain, S. H. Unger, N. R. Rosenquist and M. S. Swain, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 492.
14. M. Charton and B. Charton, *Bulletin De La Societe Chimique De France*, 1988, 199.
15. M. Harati and M. R. Gholami, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2005, **37**, 90.
16. O. Banjoko and I. A. Babatunde, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 8035.
17. J. Shorter, "Correlation Analysis of Organic Reactivity", Research Studies Press, Letchworth, 1982.
18. C. Reichardt, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1979, **18**, 98.